

Dusting off ancient anthropometric data banks

The “Mainz Punch Card Archive” and “Geneva ADAM” and their integration with the updated and enlarged LiVES-COstA online database

Julia Ebert^{*1}, Robert Martin², Jocelyne Desideri³, Marie Besse⁴, Winfried Henke⁵, Marcus Groß⁶ and Eva Rosenstock^{*7}

* Corresponding authors

¹ Institut für Prähistorische Archäologie, Freie Universität Berlin, Fabeckstraße 23-25, 14915 Berlin, julia.ebert@fu-berlin.de

² Institut für Prähistorische Archäologie, Freie Universität Berlin, Fabeckstraße 23-25, 14915 Berlin

³ Laboratoire d'archéologie préhistorique et anthropologie, Section des sciences de la Terre et de l'environnement & Institut des sciences de l'environnement, Université de Genève, Uni Carl Vogt, 66 boulevard Carl Vogt, CH - 1211 Genève 4

⁴ Laboratoire d'archéologie préhistorique et anthropologie, Section des sciences de la Terre et de l'environnement & Institut des sciences de l'environnement, Université de Genève, Uni Carl Vogt, 66 boulevard Carl Vogt, CH - 1211 Genève 4, Marie.Besse@unige.ch, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4752-9070>

⁵ Institute of Organismic and Molecular Evolution, Anthropology, Johannes Gutenberg-University Mainz, Colonel-Kleinmann-Weg 2, 55099 Mainz, henkew@uni-mainz.de

⁶ INWT Statistics GmbH, Obentrautstr. 72, 12063 Berlin

⁷ Freie Universität Berlin, Institut für Prähistorische Archäologie, Fabeckstraße 23-25, 14915 Berlin; Einstein Center Chronoi, Otto-von-Simson-Str. 7, 14195 Berlin, e.rosenstock@fu-berlin.de, <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-6693-4303>

Abstract

The research project LiVES (living conditions and biological standard of living in prehistoric Europe and South West Asia), funded by the Emmy-Noether-Programme of the German Research Foundation (DFG) and running from 2011 to 2019, focused – among other things – on the relationship between protein-intake and body height in prehistoric humans as a possible proxy for health and diet (e.g. Rosenstock 2014; Hujic 2016; Scheibner 2016). In order to obtain a sufficient amount of data relating to prehistoric body heights within the project's timespan, which could then be correlated with relevant environmental, chronological and socio-historic variables,

it was necessary to acquire and convert datasets from two already existing data collections: the Mainzer Lochkartenarchiv für prähistorische und historische Anthropologie (Mainz punch card archive for prehistoric and historic anthropology) and the Geneva-based Anthropological Data Acquisition and Management (ADAM); they were eventually integrated with a new and regularly updated online database LiVES Collection of Osteological Anthropometry (LiVES-COstA) which, aside from our own purposes, is intended for future use by academic institutions and individual researchers around the world. With checked and published data from 6901 skeletal individuals dating up to 600 cal BCE, and a total of 18,127 unchecked, unpublished skeletal entries mostly dating to later periods, it is currently the largest digital collection of prehistoric and historic human long bone and stature data from Europe and Southwest Asia. In this article we will give a detailed report on the data acquisition and integration process within the framework of the LiVES-project, and describe the structure, as well as the state of data at the end of the project. Also, we will give a very brief summary on the publication of those datasets that have been checked and updated by the LiVES project in the LiVES-COstA Digest-collection.

Preludes to the LiVES-COstA database

The roots of our data collection date back to 2006, when, within the research of the chair of economic history at the University of Tübingen, Nikola Köpke and Eva Rosenstock extended the data collection activity of Jörg Baten's group on Classical to modern skeletal data to also include prehistorical individuals. While the historical data in this collection of postcranial measurements and body height estimations formed the core of Nikola Köpke's research (e.g. Köpke - Baten 2005; 2008; Köpke 2016) and is one of the roots of the Backbone of Europe project (Steckel et al. 2018), the prehistoric entries later constituted the core of the LiVES project. The data were compiled in Microsoft Access format. By 2014, the Tübingen – and later LiVES – Access-database contained 272 sites with 2614 individuals. However, it had been clear from the beginning that the Access-database format did not provide the necessary capacity for the number of records to be used for our final analyses and data modelling. It was even less suitable for handling the additional data from the two older data banks, the Mainz archive and Geneva ADAM, which were acquired by the LiVES project in 2008 and 2014, respectively.

Aside from generating a large sample for statistical analysis, another aim of this large-scale data collection (and revision) was to eventually make the information contained in these various data sources available to the public in compact form for further research purposes. Thus, in 2014 all data collections were transferred and merged into a single regularly updated MySQL online-database with PHPMyAdmin administration surface. Additionally, the updated and checked parts serving as the underlying sample to a number of papers (Rosenstock 2014; 2015a;b; Rosenstock et al. 2015; Groß 2016; Rosenstock - Scheibner 2018; Rosenstock et al. in press; in prep.) were published online on the 'Edition TOPOI' website (Rosenstock et al. 2019). LiVES-COstA possibly represents one of the largest (pre-)historic anthropometric data collections worldwide, beside that of the "Global History of Human Health Project" based at Ohio State University in Columbus (Steckel et al. 2018), and, to our knowledge, includes the largest database for prehistoric long

bone and stature data for the period up to ca. 600 BCE in Europe (see also Ruff et al. 2018) and West Asia. Its constituent databases as well as the process of data integration, updating and publication are described here.

The Mainz punch card archive

The data collection of the Mainz punch card archive forms an important component of the LiVES-database. It was founded in 1967, following a proposal by the Swiss anthropologist Marc-Rodolphe Sauter (1914-1983) at the conference of the Association des Anthropologistes de langue française, which took place in Brussels in November of that year (Schwidetzky - Creel 1971, 41). The Mainz database had initially been intended as a databank for prehistoric anthropology, more specifically as a “banque néolithique”. However, as preparations progressed, it was decided that its scientific value should be increased by widening its scope to include data sets from both prehistoric as well as historic periods, beginning with the Mesolithic (Schwidetzky - Creel 1971, 41). The database project was headed by Ilse Schwidetzky of the Anthropological Institute of the University of Mainz, Germany, received additional funding from the Wenner-Gren- Foundation in 1969 (Schwidetzky 1984).

Data formats and structure

The data bank was originally devised as an archive of punch and index cards. As most of the original cards have not survived, we can – with the exception of the surviving literature index cards¹ - only reconstruct its structure from the few published accounts of it, such as Schwidetzky - Creel 1971, Perscheid 1974 and Schwidetzky – Jäger 1991. In its initial stage, the original punch card archive was focused on cranial traits and therefore contained 32 craniometric measurements, and only 4 complementary postcranial measurements (maximum lengths of femur, tibia, humerus and radius), as well as information on age and sex, burial number and an individual ID for each skeleton or aggregated skeletal series. In 1972, several further postcranial measurements were added and recorded on an additional set of punch cards (Perscheid 1974). The selection of measurements was adopted from the Geneva ADAM (see below), which had been conceptualized at the same time as the Mainz archive, going back to an agreement between the two institutions to share the task of establishing a data collection of prehistoric human skeletal material (Menk 1981, 331). It should also be mentioned that all measures in both the Mainz and the Geneva ADAM data banks conform to the definitions given by Martin 1928. Each card of either set was referenced by another punch card set with contextual information on the associated series. These included site name, country, geographic position with latitude and longitude, number of male and female, and undetermined adults and subadults, relative date/cultural attribution, upper and lower absolute dating, as well as short (author-year) bibliographical references. A fourth set of 1570 index cards (Fig. 1) contained these short

¹ Archived at the successor of the Institut für Anthropologie at Mainz University, i.e. the Institut für Organismische und Molekulare Evolutionsbiologie, Anthropologie and as tiff images at the Institut für Prähistorische Archäologie, Freie Universität Berlin.

citations, the full literature reference and all ID numbers of the skeletal series related to the publication, as well as – if applicable - the ID of the respective offprint in the collection at the library of the Mainz institute.

Fig. 1: Scanned image of an exemplary index card from the Mainz data bank. Series numbers are arranged in rows on the left, the literature reference is placed in the middle, and in the upper right corner the reference number for the respective offprints is given. The complex layout, handwritten additions and corrections, as well as – in other cases – special characters from various languages, complicated the conversion into MS Excel-format.

Likely instigated by the digital activities of the Geneva ADAM collection (see below), the then technical assistant for the database, Hans-Jürgen Jäger, was entrusted with the conversion of the Mainz archive into dbf-format between 1990 and 1995. Probably for reasons of maximum file size in the early 1990s, the contents of the cards containing up to 32 cranial as well as four postcranial measurements were divided into 14 files. The first five files, “datba1” to “datba5”, contained Paleolithic, Mesolithic, Neolithic, Bronze and Iron Age data, respectively. “Datba6a” to “datba6c” contained Roman data, “datba7a” to “datba7c” data from the Migration Period to the Early Medieval, and “datba8a” to “datba8c” comprised data from the Late Medieval to the Modern Period. The postcranial data cards added in the 1970s were stored in a file “pocra”, while the file containing the data cards with contextual information was called “Vorlauf” (Fig. 2a, 2b). Also owing to the technical possibilities of that time, the bibliographical index cards were not digitized. From that point on, these digital copies and the paper literature cards represented the only extant version of the Mainz data bank, as the original punch cards were apparently

destroyed after completion of this process. Unfortunately, when Winfried Henke, safekeeper of this legacy data, gave a copy of the database to Eva Rosenstock in 2008, the Bronze Age cranial data (datba4) were missing from the memory media for unknown reasons - reminding us of the importance of archiving hard copies whenever possible.

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N
SERIE	ORT	LAND	KOOR	KULTUR	UNTERZEIT	OBERZEIT	MAEN	FRAL	KINDI	ADUL	UK	LANGAUTOR	
1	1 NAZLET KHATER	AEGY	31E27	PALAEOLITHIKUM SPAET	-35000	-30000	1M					THOMA 1984	
2	2 QAFZEH	ISR	35E33	PALAEOLITHIKUM SPAET	-40000	-35000	2M	2W				VANDERMEERSCH 1981	
3	3 SKHUL	ISR	34E32	PALAEOLITHIKUM SPAET	-60000	-30000	4M	2W	2K		4L	MCCOWN, KEITH 1939	
4	4 ARENE CANDIDE	ITAL	8E45	GRAVETTIIEN	-27000	-19000	1M					FRAYER UNV.	
5	5 AVELINE'S HOLE	ENG	3W52	MAGDALENIEN	-16000	-10000		1W				FRAYER UNV.	
6	6 BARMA GRANDE	ITAL	7E44	MAGDALENIEN	-16000	-10000	2M					FRAYER UNV.	
7	7 BRNO	CSSR	18E50	AURIGNACIEN	-33000	-26000	1M	2W				FRAYER UNV.	
8	8 BRUNIQUEL	FRANK	1E45	MAGDALENIEN	-16000	-10000		1W				FRAYER UNV.*	
9	9 CAP BLANC	FRANK	1E45	MAGDALENIEN	-16000	-10000		1W				FRAYER UNV.*	
10	10 CAVIGLIONE	ITAL	7E44	GRAVETTIIEN	-27000	-19000	1M					FRAYER UNV.*	
11	11 CHANCELADE	FRANK	8E46	MAGDALENIEN	-16000	-10000	1M					FRAYER UNV.*	
12	12 CHEDDAR	ENG	3W52	MAGDALENIEN	-16000	-10000	1M					FRAYER UNV.	
13	13 CIOCL OVINA	RUM	23E46	AURIGNACIEN	-33000	-26000		1W				FRAYER UNV.*	
14	14 COMBE-CAPELLE	FRANK	8E45	CHATELPERRONIEN	-34000	-30000	1M					FRAYER UNV.*	
15	15 COTTES	FRANK	8E47	AURIGNACIEN	-33000	-26000			1A			FRAYER UNV.*	
16	16 CRO MAGNON	FRANK	1E45	AURIGNACIEN	-33000	-26000	2M	1W				FRAYER UNV.	
17	17 DOLNI VESTONICE	CSSR	18E49	GRAVETTIIEN	-27000	-19000		3W				FRAYER UNV.	
18	18 DURUTHY (SORDE)	FRANK	1E44	MAGDALENIEN	-16000	-10000	1M	2W				FRAYER UNV.*	
19	19 FLINT JACK'S CAVE	ENG	3W52	MAGDALENIEN	-16000	-10000		1W				FRAYER UNV.	
20	20 GROTTE DES ENFANTS	FRANK	7E44	AURIGNACIEN	-33000	-26000	2M	1W				FRAYER UNV.	
21	21 LES HOTEAUX	FRANK	5E46	MAGDALENIEN	-16000	-10000		1W		1A		FRAYER UNV.*	
22	22 ISTURITS	FRANK	2W44	AURIGNACIEN	-33000	-26000						FRAYER UNV.*	
23	23 KENT'S CAVERN	ENG	4W51	MAGDALENIEN	-16000	-10000		1W				FRAYER UNV.	
24	24 KOSTENKI ZAMYATNIN	UKR	39E52	MAGDALENIEN	-16000	-10000	1M					FRAYER UNV.*	
25	25 KOSTENKI MARKINA GOR	UKR	39E52	MAGDALENIEN	-16000	-10000	1M					FRAYER UNV.*	
26	26 LAUGERIE-BASSE	FRANK	1E45	MAGDALENIEN	-16000	-10000		2W				FRAYER UNV.*	
27	27 MLADEC	CSSR	17E50	AURIGNACIEN	-33000	-26000	3M	2W		1A		FRAYER UNV.	
28	28 OBERKASSEL	BRD	7E51	MAGDALENIEN	-16000	-10000	1M	1W				FRAYER UNV.	
29	29 OLMO	ITAL	11E44	MAGDALENIEN	-16000	-10000				1A		FRAYER UNV.*	
30	30 PAGLICCI	ITAL	13E42	GRAVETTIIEN	-27000	-19000	1M					FRAYER UNV.	
31	31 ABRI PATAUD	FRANK	1E45	GRAVETTIIEN	-27000	-19000		1W				FRAYER UNV.	

(a)

SERIE	IND	SEX	AGE	H1	R1	F1	T1	C1	C6	S1	S2	H5
70234	107		1	7	0	0	481	375	0	0	0	0
70741	2201		2	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
70234	8P		1	7	0	0	433	357	0	0	0	0
30236	3		1	4	0	0	0	280	0	0	0	0
70234	82		1	7	0	258	0	397	0	0	0	0
70234	68		3	7	0	0	433	354	0	0	0	0
70234	63		1	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
70234	60		1	7	0	0	439	352	0	0	0	0
30251	5		1	7	0	0	0	365	0	0	0	0
30251	6		1	7	0	0	0	450	0	0	0	0
70234	24		3	7	0	0	428	344	0	0	0	0
70249	1		1	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
30253	32		5	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
70249	10		1	7	0	0	0	0	130	41	0	0
70233	97		3	7	0	0	407	342	0	0	0	0
70233	903		1	7	0	0	478	387	0	0	0	0
70233	9		1	7	0	0	463	0	0	0	0	0
70233	89		1	7	0	0	438	367	0	0	0	0
30253	48		3	7	0	0	418	0	0	0	0	0
70233	87		3	7	0	0	423	0	0	0	0	0
70233	651		1	7	0	0	463	0	0	0	0	0
70233	634		3	7	0	0	430	0	0	0	0	0
70233	630		1	7	0	0	0	418	0	0	0	0
70233	626		1	7	0	0	475	408	0	0	0	0
30253	49		5	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
70234	158		3	7	0	0	0	335	0	0	0	0
70249	21		3	7	0	0	0	0	122	32	0	0
70249	8		1	7	0	0	0	0	145	39	0	0

(b)

Fig. 2: Screenshot of the digitised data from the Mainz data bank; a) “Vorlauf”-table containing contextual data for the skeletal series (equivalent to locations); b) “pocra”-table containing individual postcranial measurements with series-numbers and unique identifiers.

Prehistoric and historic anthropometric data

The Mainz archive was maintained by Ilse Schwidetzky and her colleagues until the late 1980s, and the dates of the publications the data were gathered from range from 1895 to 1988. The geographical scope of the database ranges from Siberia to Southwest Europe and from Northeast Africa to Finland, and its temporal scope from the Paleolithic to the 20th century. Judging from the digitized version, it contains information on a total of 4551 skeletal collections (“Serien”, corresponding with findspot/layer), only 518 of which included postcranial measurements (5756 individual data sets without aggregated data). The number of individual datasets with cranial measurements is much higher, amounting to 44,269. This circumstance highlights the primary interest in cranial features that had long been prevalent in physical anthropology, as they were thought to be associated with specific ethnic traits/groups - not just general populations such as European or African (for reference and more detailed discussions of this subject see, for example, Lüddecke 2000; Massin 1999; Etzemüller 2015).

Much of the content in the Mainz archive also reflects one of Schwidetzky’s main research interests, i.e. the “racial” composition of prehistoric, historic and recent Eastern European populations, and she often used the data she obtained from relevant studies in order to illustrate “racial” continuity or discontinuity within a specific geographic region. This can be inferred, for instance, by the subject matter of her habilitation thesis “Rassenkunde der Altslawen” (Schwidetzky 1938) or her later contributions to the “Fundamenta” publication project which covers the prehistoric period from the Mesolithic until the Bronze Age (Schwidetzky 1973, 1978). However, while the data bank comprises numerous prehistoric individuals, it also includes a larger number of historic and even rather recent datasets, i.e. from the 19th and early (and possibly mid-)20th centuries AD. At least the origin and publishing of these latter ones can be considered ethically problematic, such as measurements from the crania of “Zigeuner” (“Gypsies”) which were derived from a study published by Sophie Ehrhardt (1969), who had been actively involved in Nazi eugenics related to Romani people (Grün 2004; Hohmann 1991, esp. 325 ff.; Vogel 1985). This aspect pertaining to the connection between the history of physical anthropology in Germany and its implications for the development and contents of the Mainz and ADAM data banks, will be discussed in more detail in a separate study (Ebert in prep.).

Geneva data bank (ADAM)

Data formats and structure

Like the Mainz Archive, the Geneva ADAM, too, originated from the anthropologists’ conference in 1967, and during the first few years of its use, also comprised a file of punch cards. Since the University of Geneva Department of Anthropology did not possess its own hardware to handle these cards, a different data management solution had to be found (Menk 1981). This led to the development of specific (fully computerized) database software programmed in FORTRAN by Roland Menk, who later became senior assistant at the Institute of Anthropology (Gallay 1985).

The program permitted the inclusion of a much broader set of parameters and various types of information, which could then be linked to each other much more easily (Menk 1981). The data could be stored digitally on floppy discs or magnetic tape. As a further notable outcome of this technical enhancement, the purpose of the data bank was no longer restricted to addressing specific anthropological research questions, as it was the case with the Mainz data bank, but was widened in such a way that it could potentially serve as a collection of information for any interdisciplinary research enquiry. In 1979, the data bank comprised as many as 71 contextual and 772 morphometric and morphoscopic variables, which could be expanded further if required (Menk 1981).

Another underlying motivation for this undertaking was the need for Menk to accumulate and analyse a large amount of data for his PhD thesis on the anthropology of the European Neolithic, for which he applied multivariate statistical methods (Menk 1975; 1977). Due to Menk's unexpected early death in 1985, work on the database came to a halt, and those responsible at the Geneva department - then headed by Christian Simon (1941-2000) - had to react quickly and took measures to preserve and transfer the data bank to a more user friendly system. This was achieved in 1989, when the database was run on an SQL-based system. It appears as if it has not been updated since then, so this marks the final state of data collection with 4196 sites and 52,851 individuals (Bertato et al. 2003). Finally, in June 1999, the structure of ADAM was changed to facilitate migration to a University server (Fig. 3). It was now implemented in Oracle and could be operated and analysed with various data management tools, such as Microsoft Access, Excel or IBM's SPSS (Bertato et al. 2003). It is not, however, publicly accessible, but can be accessed upon request to the laboratory via Marie Besse.

The query options for ADAM online are very limited, i.e. one can either search for specific bones, sites, or basic information on the skeletal data from a specific site, each with site information displayed on the same results page. Each data set is linked to a specific site via a unique site ID. The last technical update of the ADAM website site was performed in 2003, and the data include a maximum of 60 contextual parameters, as well as a total of 1030 possible anthropometric measurements (Bertato et al. 2003). Contextual variables include continent, country, general locality, specific site name, geographic longitude and latitude in decimal degrees, number of individuals, as well as relative and absolute chronological attribution and a short citation of the referenced literature.

Prehistoric, historic and recent skeletal data

The number of series in the ADAM database is comparable to that of the Mainz Archive, which may partly be a consequence of the fact that exchange of data between those responsible for each collection took place on a regular basis. This is, among other things, evident from the list of contextual variables in Menk's FORTRAN program, which, in addition to a unique internal ID, includes a field for the serial number of the "Lochkartenarchiv Mainz". However, since the ADAM database was supposed to be as exhaustive as possible, postcranial measurements also form a

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL [https://wacap.unige.ch/3346/pls/topaca/sqlid11w\\$femur.actionquery](https://wacap.unige.ch/3346/pls/topaca/sqlid11w$femur.actionquery). The main content is a table with columns: Site_Id, Sqe_Identifier, Sqe_Sex, Sqe_Age, Sqe_Age_Between, Mfem1l, Mfem1r, Mfem2l, Mfem2r, Mfem7al, Mfem7ar, Mfem7l, Mfem7r, Mfem7x, Mfem8al, Mfem8ar, Mfem8x. The table contains 51 rows of data for Site_Id 74. To the right of the table, there is a summary of site information:

- Site_Id: 74
- Nbe_Squelettes: 51
- Nbe_Femur: 49
- Cont: EUROPE
- Ctry: GERMANY
- Lct: GROSSBREMBACH
- Latit: 51.06
- Longit: 11.19
- Ch_g: BRONZE-AGE-EARLY
- Chrl: AUNJETTIZ

Fig. 3: Screenshot of the ADAM-online database showing the table containing individual femur measurement. For each skeletal individual a unique identifier, as well as information on sex and age are provided. Contextual information associated with the site (location) is displayed in a separate partition on the right.

much larger part of the overall amount of data, while they were in many cases missing from the Mainz data bank, which was mainly intended for recording cranial data.

The geographic scope and amount of more recent data is even larger in ADAM than it is in the Mainz data bank; this is to a large extent due to Roland Menk's research interests, as well as his and his colleagues' commitment to encouraging researchers around the world to provide the data that they collected to the Geneva ADAM – including unpublished material (Menk 1981; Gallay 1985). Among the numerous project collaborations Menk had established with Swiss and foreign anthropologists throughout his time at the Anthropological Institute of the University of Geneva, the most notable were the paleoanthropology of early Greece and the Iron Gates region, prehistoric populations of St. Lawrence Island off the coast of Alaska, as well as an anthropological assessment of the Copper Age-Early Bronze Age transition in Hungary (Gallay 1985). Accordingly, data from those projects feature heavily in the database. Further, more recent datasets - partly of ethically dubious origin - include individuals from parts of Africa, Canada and Australia.

Integration and editing of the Mainz, ADAM and LiVES data collections

Digitization of the Mainz literature cards

When work on the Mainz database was resumed by Winfried Henke and Eva Rosenstock in 2008, the technical possibilities in OCR scanning had reached a level that finally permitted the digitization of the literature cards. In a first step in 2009, the index cards were scanned and saved as tiff files. The relatively complex structure of the cards (Fig. 1) with columns and rows as well as vertical and horizontal dividing lines required the use of sophisticated tailor-programmed character recognition software to convert the content into MS Excel format. This process was kindly conducted by the firm SRZ digitization and publishing based in Berlin. Special characters from other languages as well as other manual additions, however, could not be transmitted correctly, and therefore many entries had to be corrected or newly entered using the tiff images manually in 2011. In addition, journal titles on the index cards were abbreviated and could not always be readily attributed to the corresponding journals.

Combining the LiVES, Mainz and Geneva data collections

In 2014, Jocelyne Desideri and Marie Besse granted Eva Rosenstock access to the ADAM database and the merging of the LiVES, Mainz and Geneva ADAM collections could be accomplished by 2015. The new database LiVES-Collection of Osteological Anthropometry (LiVES-COstA) incorporates all three collections in a php/MySQL online-database and consists of six tables (Fig. 4). Similarly to the “Vorlauf” table in the Mainz database, the “location”-table contains relevant contextual information on a layer, such as site name, country, relative chronological, as well as absolute dating span (lower and upper date), geographic latitude, longitude (WGS84-coordinates in decimal degrees), layer, source database and type of burial and is linked to the table “individuals” which contains the anthropometric skeletal data. Another table “literature” comprises bibliographical details for the sites, which are linked to the “locations” table via the “location_literature”-table. A table named “ADAM_extension” contains additional postcranial measurements that are rarely available and not relevant for our analyses but needed to be integrated for reasons of completeness. Moreover, the database features the table “cranium” with numerous craniometric measurements taken over from the Mainz Archive (dbf file) only, since importing these data from ADAM also would have resulted in too many duplicate entries which we could not possibly have edited due to time restrictions, and also because the cranial data were not relevant for our object of research. The Mainz cranial data collection is, however, still valuable as a data source for other anthropologists.

The new online database has a user-friendly front end (Fig. 5a, 5b) that permits simple data management operations such as searching, inserting, importing and exporting data sets, while more complex operations can be done using SQL queries.

Fig. 4: Graphic scheme showing the structure of the LiVES-COstA online-database.

Checking and updating of the Mainz and Geneva entries

Despite the existence of a field in ADAM that indicated site doubles with the Mainz database stemming from the active exchange of data between the two institutions at least until the end of the 1970s (Schwidetzky - Jäger 1991, 164), deleting or merging duplicate entries constituted one of the major tasks of the data checking process. Since ADAM occasionally contained postcranial data, while the same site in the Mainz database had no postcranial data, all datasets from both the Geneva ADAM and the Mainz database had to be imported. Moreover, the MS Access data collection first established in Tübingen contained several sites which also existed in one or both of the older databases. At present, the data from approx. 650 duplicate sites were deleted or merged with other entries for the same skeletal series.

Apart from occasional comma errors, particularly the geographic position, relative date/cultural attribution and absolute dating of many entries needed extensive updating. In the Mainz database, latitude and longitude of a location were only provided as a rough orientation in degrees of the Northwest corner of the respective grid square. Since this information is too inaccurate for reliably locating and displaying the sites on a map, in the revised version the geographic location is provided as decimal World Geodetic System 1984 (WGS84) coordinates, with two digits after decimal point. For the purposes of LiVES, i.e. displaying and analyzing a large number of sites in Europe and South West Asia, this degree of accuracy was considered sufficient.

The relative chronological information in both the Geneva ADAM and the Mainz databases was in many cases not very precise or even entirely outdated, ranging from minor flaws such as the attribution of the Großgartach-culture site of Heilbronn-Großgartach to the Stichbandkeramik culture (location ID 406) to major blurs such as “Megalithgrab” as a relative date for the site of Lenzen (location ID 255). Due to the fact that the collections predated the Radiocarbon Revolution, absolute dates were usually not based on 14C-dates at all or on uncalibrated 14C-

dates at best. The Linear Pottery Culture, for instance, was falsely dated between 4500 and 3500 BCE.

The second extensive task concerns the revision and updating of contextual information in the Mainz series: Over the last 30 years, an abundance of new publications on the quality and chronology of the sites has become available and was continuously incorporated into the collection. Since only roughly 1/9 of the Mainz series have associated postcranial data – also because available measurements were not always entered into the data bank – it was necessary to again check the respective old and new literature references for any missing or newly published anthropometric details on the respective sites – this should also be kept in mind when working with unchecked data from the LiVES-COstA database. Parallel to this, research for literature on new sites with available postcranial or body height data was carried out.

Current state of data maintenance and publication

Presently, 314 site entries from the Mainz Archive have been checked, updated, and supplemented, while the total number of checked and new locations is 775 (Fig. 6). These contain 6449 individuals in 4836 data sets (including data sets with aggregated individuals and/or body height estimates only). Concentrating on the target period of the LiVES project, entries before the Upper Paleolithic and after the Iron Age or in absolute terms ca. 1000 BCE were only checked for duplicates and consistency as well as updated occasionally. The Mainz and Geneva ADAM data, however, cover a much larger time span. Therefore, another 18,127 individual postcranial data sets are available from the Mainz data bank which are still unchecked and date to the period after 600 BCE. All in all, the contribution of the Mainz and the Geneva ADAM archives now comprises 4471 locations, with approx. 45,000 entries for individual cranial data, and 20,774 postcranial data sets.

All checked entries are marked with a “check” field in the LiVES-COstA database and are, in addition, published online and open access as LiVES-COstA Digest (Rosenstock et al. 2019). The format developed by Edition Topoi allows for basic querying and sorting of the data as well as downloading data sets. Unlike other possible formats, such as .html or .xls (e.g. Rosenstock 2009; Ruff et al. 2018 underlying Ruff 2018), the .txt -format guarantees data compatibility in the distant digital future. The data published as LiVES-COstA Digest form the underlying sample repository for a number of studies (e.g. Rosenstock – Scheibner 2018; Rosenstock et al., in press; forthcoming).

We hope that the new LiVES-COstA Digest database will be of use for relevant anthropological and interdisciplinary studies. Updated and checked entries can be freely downloaded from the TOPOI-site, while unchecked data in the entire LiVES-COstA can only be accessed with a username and password, which we can provide to researchers with specific/relevant research objectives upon request to Eva Rosenstock.

Fig. 6: Map showing the geographic distribution of checked and updated locations in the LiVES-COstA online-database containing relevant long bone measurements or body height estimations.

Acknowledgements

The database work described here, and this paper are part of the research of the Emmy-Noether Junior Research Group “LiVES” (RO4148/1, PI Eva Rosenstock) funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG). Eva Rosenstock designed and coordinated the work, while Julia Ebert, Robert Martin and Eva Rosenstock collected and updated anthropometric data. Robert Martin updated literature data. Marcus Groß and Eva Rosenstock developed the database structure, and Jocelyne Desideri, Marie Besse and Winfried Henke provided background information on the Mainz and ADAM Geneva databases. Julia Ebert and Eva Rosenstock wrote the paper, with contributions by all authors. We thank the Romano-German Commission (RGK) of the German Archaeological Institute (DAI), namely Friedrich Lüth, for crucial support in the drafting stage of the project. We are grateful to the library project “24in1” at the Freie Universität Berlin, namely Michael Franke-Maier, and to SRZ, Berlin, namely Joachim W. Krüger, who provided invaluable help in digitizing the literature cards. We are indebted to Nikola Köpke and Jörg Baten for the permission to use datasets created jointly in Tübingen in 2006. We thank INWT Statistics, Berlin, namely Amit Ghosh, Steffen Wagner and Martin Badicke, for their support in creating an SQL platform for the data, and we thank Freie Universität Berlin, namely Johannes Posel, for permanent hosting of the LiVES-COstA database. We are indebted to the Excellence

Cluster TOPOI, namely Gerd Graßhoff, Michael Meyer, André Renis and Gisela Eberhardt, for supporting the editing and publishing process of the LiVES-COstA Digest and the publication of this accompanying paper on both collections. Finally, thanks are due to Alisa Scheibner and Alisa Hujic for many helpful discussions on data and data structure.

References

Bertato et al. 2003

R. Bertato – G. Khalifa – R. Menk – G. Puissant – G. Schaller – F. Serena – C. Simon, La base de données anthropométriques ADAM. L'origine du projet, <http://lap.unige.ch/baseADAM/ADAM/index.html#projet> (last accessed 22.09.2018).

Ehrhardt 1969

S. Ehrhardt, Zigeunerschädel, *Homo* 20, 1969, 95–110.

Ebert, in prep.

J. Ebert, The Mainz and Geneva ADAM data collections and the field of physical anthropology in 20th century Germany. Historical context and ethical considerations about two comprehensive anthropometric data banks.

Etzemüller 2015

T. Etzemüller, Auf der Suche nach dem Nordischen Menschen. Die deutsche Rassenanthropologie in der modernen Welt, *Science Studies* 1 (Bielefeld 2015).

Gallay 1985

A. Gallay, Nécrologie. Roland Menk, 1945-1985, *Archives Suisses d'Anthropologie Générale Genève* 48, 1, 1985, 1–3.

Groß 2016

M. Groß, Modeling body height in prehistory using a spatio-temporal Bayesian errors-in variables model, *Advances in Statistical Analysis* 2016, doi:10.1007/s10182-015-0260-x

Grün 2004

B. Grün, Sophie Ehrhardt (1902-1990). Anthropologin und "Zigeunerforscherin", <<http://www.uni-tuebingen.de/frauenstudium/biographien/biographien.html>> (last accessed 5 May 2015).

Hujić 2016

Alisa Hujic, Das Kind in uns unter der Lupe der Isotopie, Allometrie und Pathologie. Zusammenhang zwischen $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ und $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ als Eiweißproxy und dem longitudinalen Knochenwachstum bei adulten, prähistorischen Skelettindividuen unter Berücksichtigung weiterer Indikatoren für Nährstoffversorgung, Dissertation FU Berlin 2016, http://www.diss.fu-berlin.de/diss/receive/FUDISS_thesis_000000101262?lang=en (last accessed 7 May 2018).

Köpke 2016

N. Köpke, The Biological Standard of Living on Europe from the Late Iron Age to the Little Ice Age, in: J. Komlos - I.R. Kelly (eds.), *The Oxford Handbook of Economics and Human Biology* (New York 2016) 70-108.

Lüddecke 2000

A. Lüddecke, Rassen, Schädel und Gelehrte. Zur politischen Funktionalität der anthropologischen Forschung und Lehre in der Tradition Egon von Eickstedts, Geschichte und ihre Hilfswissenschaften 880 (Frankfurt/Main et al. 2000).

Martin 1928

R. Martin, Lehrbuch der Anthropologie. In systematischer Darstellung mit besonderer Berücksichtigung der anthropologischen Methoden: für Studierende, Ärzte und Forschungsreisende 2(Jena 1928).

Massin 1999

B. Massin, Anthropologie und Humangenetik oder: Wie schreiben deutsche Wissenschaftler ihre eigene Wissenschaftsgeschichte?, in: H. Kaupen-Haas – C. Saller (eds.), Wissenschaftlicher Rassismus. Analysen einer Kontinuität in den Human- und Naturwissenschaften (Frankfurt/Main u.a. 1999) 12–64.

Menk 1981 [1979]

R. Menk, Data Banks in Historical Anthropology. The Material Infrastructure for Interdisciplinarity, in: R. Menk – A. Gallay (eds.), Anthropologie et Archéologie. le cas des premières âges des Métaux. Actes du Symposium de Sils-Maria 25–30 septembre 1978, Archives Suisses d'Anthropologie Générale (Numéro spécial) 43 Fasc. 2 (Geneva 1981 [1979]) 331–341.

Menk 1977

R. Menk, La Néolithisation. Impact de l'innovation culturelle sur la biologie et la dynamique des populations, Archives Suisses d'Anthropologie Générale Genève 41,1, 1977, 31–35.

Menk 1975

R. Menk, Anthropologie du Néolithique Européen. Analyse multivariée et essai de synthèse, Genève, Univ., Diss., (Geneva 1975).

Perscheid 1974

M. Perscheid, Das Mainzer Lochkartenarchiv für postkraniales Skelettmaterial prähistorischer Populationen, Homo 25, 1974, 121–124.

Rosenstock 2009

E. Rosenstock, Tells in Südwestasien und Südosteuropa: Entstehung, Verbreitung und Definition eines Siedlungsphänomens (=Urgeschichtliche Studien II) (Grunbach 2009).

Rosenstock 2014

E. Rosenstock, Eiweißversorgung und Körperhöhe: Zur Übertragbarkeit anthropometrischer Ansätze auf die Archäologie, in: W. Schier/M. Meyer (Hrsg.), Vom Nil bis an die Elbe. Forschungen aus fünf Jahrzehnten am Institut für Prähistorische Archäologie der Freien Universität Berlin, Internationale Archäologie – Studia honoraria 36 (Rahden/Westfalen 2014) 147-163.

Rosenstock 2015a

E. Rosenstock, Grown up. Adult Height Dimorphism as an Archive of Living Conditions of Boys and Girls in Prehistory, in: G. Coşkunsu (ed.), *The Archaeological Study of Childhood: Interdisciplinary Perspectives on an Archaeological Enigma*. Proceedings of the IEMA Postdoctoral Visiting Scholar Conference on Theories and Methods in Archaeology 3, April 2010, The Institute for European and Mediterranean Archaeology Distinguished Monograph Series (Albany 2015) 107-127.

Rosenstock 2015b

E. Rosenstock, The Prize of Urbanization? Biological Standard of Living in the Near East around the 4th millennium, in: M. B. d'Anna - C. Jauß - J. C. Johnson (eds.), with individual contributions by (in order of appearance) K. Wagensohn, C. Jauß, S. Pollock, E. Rosenstock, R. Berthon, J. Dahl, J. C. Johnson, M. B. D'Anna and H. Brunke, *Food and Urbanization. Material and Textual Perspectives on Alimentary Practice in Early Mesopotamia*, *Origini. Rivista di Preistoria e Protostoria delle Civiltà Antiche/Prehistory and Protohistory of Ancient Civilizations XXXVII*, 2015, 37-41.

Rosenstock et al. 2015

E. Rosenstock - M. Groß - A. Hujic - A. Scheibner, Back to good shape. Biological standard of living in the Copper and Bronze Ages and the possible role of food, in: J. Kneisel - W. Kirleis - N. Taylor - M. dal Corso - V. Tiedtke (eds.), *Setting the Bronze Age Table: Production, Subsistence, Diet and Their Implications for European Landscapes*. Proceedings of the International Workshop "Socio-environmental dynamics over the last 12.000 years: the creation of landscapes III (15th -18th March 2013)" in Kiel (Bonn 2015) 121-151.

Rosenstock – Scheibner 2018

E. Rosenstock - A. Scheibner, Where Angel feared not to tread. Anthropometric approaches to food studies in Aegean and Balkan prehistory, in: M. Ivanova-Bieg/B. Athanassov/V. Petrova/D. Takarova/Ph. Stockhammer (Hrsg.), *Social Dimensions of Food in the Balkans* (Oxford 2018) 320-367.

Rosenstock et al. 2019

E. Rosenstock – J. Ebert – R. Martin – M. Groß, *The LiVES-COstA Digest*. Updated and checked entries of the LiVES Collection of Osteological Anthropometry, Edition TOPOI 2019, DOI: 10.17171/2-12-2-1

Rosenstock et al. in press

E. Rosenstock - J. Ebert - R. Martin - A. Hicketier - P. Walter - M. Groß, Human Stature in the Near East and Europe ca. 10 000 – 1000 BCE. Its spatio-temporal development in a Bayesian errors-in-variables model, *Anthropological and Archaeological Sciences*, AASC-D-19-00002.1. DOI: 10.1007/s12520-019-00850-3

Rosenstock et al., in prep.

E. Rosenstock – J. Ebert – A. Scheibner - P. Walter, Human stature as a proxy for nutrition in prehistory? A correlation of stable isotope and stature data ca. 10 000 to 1000 BCE.

Ruff 2018

Christopher B. Ruff (ed.), *Skeletal Variation and Adaptation in Europeans. Upper Paleolithic to the Twentieth Century* (Hoboken 2018).

Ruff et al. 2018

European data set: Excel file and Notes relating to Ruff 2018

<https://www.hopkinsmedicine.org/fae/CBR.html> (Last accessed 13 March 2019; Last update 25 May 2018).

Scheibner 2016

A. Scheibner, *Prähistorische Ernährung in Vorderasien und Europa. Eine kulturgeschichtliche Synthese auf der Basis ausgewählter Quellen, Schriften zum Lebensstandard in der Vorgeschichte 1; Berliner Archäologische Forschungen* (Rahden 2016).

Schwidetzky 1938

I. Schwidetzky, *Rassenkunde der Altslawen, Breslau, Univ., Diss., 1938* (Stuttgart 1938).

Schwidetzky 1973

I. Schwidetzky (ed.), *Die Anfänge des Neolithikums vom Orient bis Nordeuropa, Fundamenta. Reihe B Bd. 3 VIII a: Anthropologie 1. Teil* (Köln, Wien 1973).

Schwidetzky 1978

I. Schwidetzky (ed.), *Die Anfänge des Neolithikums vom Orient bis Nordeuropa, Fundamenta. Reihe B Bd. 3 VIII b: Anthropologie 2. Teil* (Köln, Wien 1978).

Schwidetzky 1984

I. Schwidetzky, *Data Banks and Multivariate Statistics in Physical Anthropology*, in: G. N. Vark – W. W. Howells (eds.), *Multivariate Statistical Methods in Physical Anthropology. A Review of Recent Advances and Current Developments* (Dordrecht 1984) 283–288.

Schwidetzky – Creel 1971

I. Schwidetzky – N. Creel, *Das Mainzer Lochkartenarchiv für die prähistorische Anthropologie*, *Homo* 22, 1971, 41–42.

Schwidetzky – Jäger 1991

I. Schwidetzky – H.-J. Jäger, *The Data Base for prehistorical and historical anthropology in Mainz*, *Homo* 42, 1991, 163–170.

Steckel et al. 2018

R. H. Steckel – C. S. Larsen – C. A. Roberts – J. Baten (eds.), *The Backbone of Europe. Health, Diet, Work and Violence over two millennia, Cambridge studies in biological and evolutionary anthropology 80* (Cambridge, United Kingdom 2018).

Vogel 1985

C. Vogel, Ethische Überlegungen zur Anthropologie und Ethologie, in: Max-Planck-Gesellschaft, München (ed.), Verantwortung und Ethik in der Wissenschaft. Symposium der Max-Planck-Gesellschaft Schloß Ringberg/Tegernsee, Mai 1984 (München 1985) 115-136.